

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

**Protocol for Farmer Feces collection
and
Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)**

[Compartment 9]

**Version 1
May/2020**

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Protocol for Farmer Feces collection and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

A. Description

Compilation the sampling of farmer feces and points, and further laboratory analysis, ensuring harmonization of testing procedures, which will enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe. This protocol will allow answering to different questions from the FED-AMR project.

B. Equipment and material

- Sterile propylene flasks, 50ml
- Sterile plastic bags
- Sterile disposable wooden spatula
- Scale
- Sterile cryotubes

C. Procedure

1. Sampling, transportation and conservation

Each participating country involved in the field studies keeps a local record of anonymized study ID numbers of the farms [name, address, city, antibiotic consumption (amount and dates), and others]. No information which can lead to the identification of farms or individuals will be kept in the central database.

- Aseptically collect ideally 25 g of freshly fecal stools **by individual**, at 4 persons, at **two time points** See Sample references for farmer feces samples, and Table 1: Project Timeline sheet).
- Collection is made into clean, dry plastic jars with screw-cap lids.
- It is recommended that samples should arrive at the laboratory within 18 hours after sampling. Meanwhile stools should be stored appropriately (0°C - 5°C) under transportation or storage.
- 2 g of those freshly feces sampled are pooled [**use always** an equal amount of each of the samples in the pool from each person].
- Collected samples are introduced into a plastic bag or a screw cap container that is airtight, watertight, and suitably robust (e.g. several 50 ml sterile propylene flasks to achieve the 300 g of feces).

- Subsequently, double-packaging within sealed plastic bags prevents leakage and some cross-contamination of samples and associated packaging materials. [Note: Feces contained only in rectal exam gloves, plastic bags, or rubber-stoppered tubes are unsuitable as they are very frequently comprised by bacterial growth with gas production that can rupture plastic bags, displace stoppers, and allow leakage of the specimen].
- All containers must be clearly and completely labeled (see the coding system at the FED-AMR homepage, and as circulated in Excel file (Timeline_Sample_02_03_2020).
- Conserve immediately samples at **0°C to 5°C** (DO NOT FREEZE FECAL SAMPLES).
- Samples should be processed at the laboratory within 18 hours.

2. Sampling processing

We have 4 individual tubes from the sampling of ≥ 5 g of each farmer.

- The pool sample of 8 g in total (2 g of each sample), should be very well mixed by stirring thoroughly with a sterile disposable wooden spatula, or other sterile device, for 1-2 minutes.
- From these pools, distribute samples as follows (see Figure 1):
 - weight about 1.0 g in a cryotube (to store at -80°C as a backup, being sure that it should only be used as last resort, because eDNA will be considerably changed in this frozen sample, and bacteriology results will be also changed);
 - a total of 11 g will be used in DNA extraction as follows:
 - weight 2.75 g (2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA) for qPCR (WP2);
 - weight 2.75 g (2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA) in triplicate to be used in metagenomics (WP2);
 - weight 0.5 g for WP2 (cultivation bacteria in nutrient and minimal media; identification of *Salmonella* spp, *Escherichia coli* and others; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria);
 - weight 1 g from each animal pool for WP3 (identification of *Clostridium difficile*; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria);

Fig 1. Human feces sampling at 2 time points (composite sample) to be performed by Portugal, Estonia.

- Tubes should be labelled according to the FED-AMR coding system, to be easy to identify the sample. See information about this coding system at the FED-AMR homepage.

3. For the representativeness of sample

It is very important:

- to **use always** an equal amount of each of the fresh samples for each pools;
- to be sure that a scale with at least two decimal-points are used, to ensure correct weighing of the required amounts;
- to **mix very well** the pooled sample, before using it for DNA extraction (WP2), or bacteriology (WP2, WP3), or quantification (WP4).

4. Conservation in the lab and transport to other European regions

- for Bacteriology procedures (WP2., WP3): conserve samples at 0°C to 5°C until bacteriology be processed, which must be with fresh pooled samples [cultivable bacteria and MICs to be performed in each country];
- for Genomics (WP2): conserve samples at 0°C to 5°C until extraction of DNA; DNA extraction must be processed within the next 18h due to eDNA [using harmonized protocol; to be performed in each country];
- if any country cannot perform qPCR, WGS, and metagenomics in the respective lab, DNA should be shipped at -80°C to the receptor lab;
- for quantification in WP4.4.: feces pool is transported freezed, in 200ml dark PP or PET bottles;
- for quantification in WP4.7.: feces pool is transported freezed, in PET bottles.

5. Sample references for farmer feces samples

Estonia:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Sate
EE20-F1-Fa1	Estonia, farmers, faeces 1	Aug-20
EE20-F2-Fa2	Estonia, farmers, faeces 2	Feb-21

Portugal:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Sate
PT20-F1-Fa1	Portugal, farmers, faeces 1	jul-20
PT20-F2-Fa2	Portugal, farmers, faeces 2	abr-21

D. References:

- EFFORT protocols (e.g. D2.1., D.1.5.)
- General Collection and Handling of Fecal Samples. University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI).
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Sampling methods (Chapter I.1.1, page 1-11).
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Collection, submission and storage of diagnostic specimens (Chapter 1.1.2., page 11-22).
- Pedersen KS, Okholm E, Johansen M, Angen Ø, Jorsal SE, Nielsen JP, Bækbo P. 2015. Clinical utility and performance of sock sampling in weaner pig diarrhoea. *Prev Vet Med.*, 120: 313-320. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2015.04.015.
- Fischer J, Hille K, Ruddat I, Mellmann A, Köck R, Kreienbrock L. 2017. Simultaneous occurrence of MRSA and ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* on pig farms and in nasal and stool samples from farmers. *Vet Microbiol.*, 200: 107-113. doi: 10.1016/j.vetmic.2016.05.021